

AURES II Financial Research Template

Member State:

Author:

Date:

Interview recorded:

Quantitative part

Please fill in the following table

Financial parameter	WACC	Debt/Equity ratio	Cost of debt	Cost of equity	DSCR	Loan tenor
Wind Onshore 2018						
Wind Offshore 2018						
PV 2018						
Wind Onshore 2019						
Wind Offshore 2019						
PV 2019						